

METHOD OF IMPROVING THE TECHNIQUE OF PLAYING IN TENNIS IN FRONT OF THE NET

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6657530>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022

Accepted: 02nd June 2022

Online: 05th June 2022

KEY WORDS

improvement, physical training, vestibular stability, efficiency.

ABSTRACT

In this article, we have reviewed a complete overview of the ways in which tennis players can improve their technique of playing in front of the net. The most effective exercises were used in it.

The main technical methods when playing near the net are blows from the summer. Exits to the grid, as a rule, are the completion of the attacking combination, but the main difficulties in performing the strike itself are related to its preparation. And the reason for this is the lack of time. The experiments showed that the time for preparation available to a tennis player who has taken a position at the net is not more than 0.1 seconds. The time limit largely determines the fundamental parameters of the shock technique. First of all, this is the widespread use of a universal grip for punches on the right and left. For the technique of performing strikes from the summer, the height of the point of impact is also of great importance. With an unsuccessful, high and not very quick response from an opponent, a tennis player who goes to the net can afford a rational, for this case, swing for a powerful final blow. But the tennis player on the back line is also forced to attack with a sweeping stroke. In this case, the netter needs to

prepare to meet the ball at a mid or low point. At a mid-height point above the net, you can usually use a powerful flat kick. In this case, for an effective response, the flight speed of the ball bypassing the stroke will help. It is necessary to direct him to an unprotected area of the opponent's court, using a rigid structure (dynamics of movement on the ball, body, arm, hand) of a blocking blow. Swing in this case, can lead to loss of time, more difficult removal of the racket on the ball, a failure in the entire coordination chain. The most difficult are the strikes from the flight at a low point. The art of playing with flying in a low point is the ability not to raise the ball high. Physical training. Due to the fact that strikes from the grid from the summer are carried out mainly in forward movement, and often in the jump and without swing, it is necessary to learn how to use the energy of run and jump. To do this, you need to be able to transfer, in an unsupported position, the center of gravity upon impact, and with it the energy enclosed in the

moving body, onto the ball. In addition to the typical tennis exercises used by tennis players to develop sprint speed, jerk power in different directions, jump agility and vestibular stability, gymnastic and acrobatic exercises were added to the basis of the experimental complex of special physical training for improving the game from the summer. 1. Exercises on the bar. Swinging. Rocking followed by a range jump. 2. Exercises on the rings. Swinging. Rocking followed by a range jump. 3. The same exercises on parallel bars. 4. Flip-flops on the mat forward through the head. 5. Jumping with a running start on hands followed by somersault over the head. These exercises, if possible on the conditions, it is advisable to use three times a week, for half an hour.

Technical training. The technique, bearing in mind the movement pattern is not complicated. But this blow is used, as a rule, in extreme situations. To improve the technique of blows when playing near the net, exercises are needed that improve the skill in difficult competitive situations. When working with these exercises, I mean improving the polysyllabic tennis reaction. Reactions are divided into simple and complex. The start-up athlete's reaction is an example of a simple reaction. The athlete knows exactly in advance which of the signals will follow and what exactly his response should be. In tennis, and in many sports games, everything is much more complicated. How the opponent will play, where and how he will direct the ball - each time it is a mystery that you need to not only solve, but also to respond to as quickly as possible. An opponent can try to circle a tennis player near the net by a direct kick along the side line, an oblique kick, a candle or, in rare cases, direct the ball to his legs -

short to the middle of the net. Therefore, the reaction of a tennis player at the net is called a three-compound or four-compound. It is her and must first be developed. Otherwise, the tennis player is in serious danger. Prominent experts, with extensive experience, warned: "exercises with a monosyllabic and two-syllable response, for example: playing from the summer at the net against each other only in a predetermined direction; or actions of the reticulum, when using only low direct or oblique encircling strokes against it while completely ignoring the candles, they can, with frequent and prolonged use, blunt the three compound and four-compound reactions necessary for the netter" [4, p. 65].

Thus, the whole variety of forms and the necessary specific physical, psychological and technical components of the game at the grid is improved only in the process of a competitive meeting. And as our studies have shown, most tennis players avoid access to the net. In general, all this explains the small volume of unstable and ineffective games in the net of the leading young tennis players of Uzbekistan. To remedy the situation, along with the traditional methods of improving the game at the net, described in numerous tennis manuals, one can recommend an exercise that would significantly increase the volume of competitive practice of playing at the net. The essence of the main training exercise, a multicomponent methodological scheme for improving the game near the grid, consists of a game with a competitive score with a special task. The player performing the task must play so that the ball sent by the opponent does not touch the surface of his court. That is, all the balls, with the exception of the reception of the

serve, he must play from the summer. If the ball touches the surface of the territory of his court, then he loses the point draw. The enemy, on the other hand, plays as he sees fit, without special restrictions. This exercise, in combination with other special exercises, is applied daily, in the amount of one set played. It is advisable to select a partner to perform the exercise at the initial stage of special improvement, which is slightly weaker than the level of the main player with soft but stable kicks from the back line. If the game, at first, is not in the desired direction, the opponent, wanting to immediately circle, often hits the net or

into the net, thereby reducing the number of training strokes from the summer, then an additional task can be introduced. A partner, if he gets into the net or out during a stroke, he jumps five free kicks of the "kangaroo", to equalize the conditions, the trained tennis player, letting the ball touch the area of his court, jumps the same number of free jumps. As a rule, after this task the game becomes more saturated with training blows. The expected effect of this exercise is a memorized, lightning fast and accurate response to the opponent's actions when reaching the grid in a competitive environment.

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